

Potential Value Chains for Fast-Growing Pioneer Woody Plants in Agroforestry Systems Following a Short Rotation Management

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Example for an agroforestry alley cropping systems with hybrids of poplar.

The cultivation of fast-growing pioneer tree species such as poplars, willows, robinia, alder, birch, hornbeam, oak, and ash represent an effective solution for climate adaptation and the diversification of agricultural land use. These species not only contribute to carbon sequestration but also enhance the microclimate, biodiversity, and nutrient cycles, thereby improving the climate resilience and yield stability of agricultural production systems. Fast-growing trees also have a wide range of uses that can be exploited through new product lines and value chains.

We differentiate between material and energy utilization as well as the use of fruits.

In terms of material use there are following options, for instance:

- as raw material for the wood industry, e.g. via modern wood processing methods such as
 - scrimber (wood-based material in which round wood is first crushed and then glued together under heat and pressure to create a dense and durable material) or
 - laminated strand lumber (Composite material made of directionally arranged wood shavings that are bonded under pressure to form panels)
- in the agricultural sector as a substrate for mushroom cultivation and for the production of mulch material or plant and soil substrates
- for the production of high-quality biochar using modern pyrolysis technology at high temperatures and in absence of oxygen.

Energy utilisation has a very good ecological balance, can contribute to climate-neutral heating solutions at a regional level and is also base-load capable.

Fruit utilisation is rather rare with these tree species, but there are also opportunities for value creation here: e.g. through the use of poplar fluff.

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